

The Antibacterial Activity of *Dioscorea alata* L. Tuber Extract Using the Agar Well Diffusion Method

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ABSTRACT

The growing emergence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens highlights the need for alternative antimicrobial agents from plant sources. This study evaluated the in vitro antibacterial activity of the tuber extract of *Dioscorea alata* L. using the agar well diffusion method. A crude extract (100 mg/mL in DMSO) was tested at concentrations of 0.5–2.5 mg per well (5–25 µL) against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella* sp., and *Salmonella typhi*. Streptomycin and DMSO served as positive and negative controls, respectively. The extract exhibited selective antibacterial activity. No inhibition was observed against *S. aureus* and *Klebsiella* sp. Moderate activity was recorded against *B. subtilis* (maximum 10 mm at 25 µL), *P. aeruginosa* (maximum 11 mm at 20 µL), and *S. typhi* (maximum 13 mm at 25 µL), showing a generally concentration-dependent response. Streptomycin produced larger inhibition zones (18–22 mm), while DMSO showed no activity. Although the activity was lower than that of streptomycin, the extract showed promising antibacterial effects, suggesting its potential as a natural antimicrobial source and the need for phytochemical investigation to identify the active principles responsible for the observed activity.

Keywords: *Dioscorea alata* L., Antibacterial activity, Agar well diffusion, Antibiotic-resistant pathogens.

INTRODUCTION

Dioscorea alata L., commonly known as greater yam or purple yam, belongs to the family Dioscoreaceae. It is widely cultivated for its edible underground tubers and aerial bulbils, serving as a good source of starch. Antibiotic-resistant pathogens have become a major global health concern (WHO, 2014). The excessive and improper use of antibiotics has led to the development of multidrug-resistant bacteria, making many commonly used medicines less effective (Ventola, 2015). As a result, there is an increasing need to discover new, safe, and affordable antimicrobial agents. Medicinal plants, which have been used for centuries in traditional healing systems, are now being explored as promising natural sources of such alternatives.

Medicinal plants are valuable sources of natural bioactive compounds that can produce a wide range of biological effects. These compounds are known for their antibacterial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant activities (Sundkar et al., 2024). Because of their chemical diversity and generally fewer side effects, plant-based antimicrobial agents are considered promising alternatives to synthetic drugs. Therefore, the present study was carried out to assess the in vitro antibacterial activity of the tuber extract of *Dioscorea alata* against selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial pathogens using the agar well diffusion method. The results of this work may help provide scientific support for the potential use of this plant as a natural source of antibacterial agents.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Plant Material

Fresh tubers of *Dioscorea alata* L. (Fig. 1B) were collected from the Konkan region of Maharashtra. The plant material was carefully identified using standard floristic manuals (Naik, 1998; Singh et al., 2001; Yadav & Sardesai, 2002) to ensure correct authentication. A voucher specimen (BGP 6720) was prepared and deposited in the VH Herbarium, Department of Botany, Vivekanand Arts, Sardar Dalipsingh Commerce & Science College, Chhatrapati Sambhajnagar, Maharashtra, for future reference.

Preparation of Tuber Powder and Extracts

Collected tubers were washed, peeled where necessary, and shade-dried at room temperature until constant weight was achieved. The dried tubers were ground into coarse powder. For antibacterial assays, 1 g of tuber powder was dissolved in 10 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to prepare a stock solution of 100 mg/mL. The solution was vortexed, filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and used to prepare graded volumes of 5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 μ L for testing.

Test Microorganisms

Antibacterial activity was carried out against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Klebsiella* sp., and *Salmonella typhi*. Pure cultures were obtained from the Department of Microbiology, Yashwantrao Chavan Institute of Science, Satara, and maintained on nutrient agar slants at 4 °C. Fresh 18–24 h cultures were used for each assay.

Preparation of Inoculum

Each test bacterium was transferred into nutrient broth and incubated at 37 °C for 18–24 hours. The culture density was then adjusted to the 0.5 McFarland standard (approximately 10^8 CFU/mL) to ensure uniform inoculum concentration.

Agar Well Diffusion Method

Sterile Mueller–Hinton agar plates were prepared and uniformly swabbed with the standardized bacterial suspension. Wells of 6 mm diameter were aseptically punched into the agar, and different volumes (5–25 μ L) of the tuber extract were dispensed into the wells. Streptomycin was used as the reference antibiotic, while DMSO served as the negative control. Plates were allowed to stand for 30 minutes for diffusion and then incubated at 37 °C for 18–24 hours.

Determination of Antibacterial Activity

After incubation, the clear zones around the wells were measured in millimeters. All tests were conducted in triplicate, and the average values were recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tuber extract of *Dioscorea alata* showed selective antibacterial activity against the tested pathogens (Table 1). No inhibition was observed against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Klebsiella* sp., indicating resistance under the present conditions. However, the extract inhibited *Bacillus subtilis*, with zones ranging from 7–10 mm and a maximum effect at 25 μ L (Fig. 1C). Moderate activity was also observed against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with a maximum of 11 mm at 20 μ L (Fig. 1D) and *Salmonella typhi*, with a maximum of 13 mm at 25 μ L (Fig. 1E). In general, susceptible bacteria showed better inhibition at higher concentrations. Streptomycin produced larger zones (18–22 mm), while DMSO showed no activity.

The antibacterial effect may be due to bioactive compounds present in the tubers. Differences in bacterial response could be related to variations in cell wall structure between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Overall, the results suggest moderate antibacterial potential of *Dioscorea alata*.

Table 1. Antibacterial Activity of Tuber Extract of *D. alata*

Test organism	Concentrations	<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	Positive Control (Streptomycin)
		Zone of Inhibition	
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	05 µL	--	22 mm
	10 µL	--	22 mm
	15 µL	--	22 mm
	20 µL	--	22 mm
	25 µL	--	22 mm
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	05 µL	7 mm	19 mm
	10 µL	9 mm	19 mm
	15 µL	--	19 mm
	20 µL	8 mm	19 mm
	25 µL	10 mm	19 mm
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	05 µL	--	--
	10 µL	10 mm	--
	15 µL	8 mm	--
	20 µL	11 mm	--
	25 µL	--	--
<i>Klebsiella species</i>	05 µL	--	18 mm
	10 µL	--	18 mm
	15 µL	--	18 mm
	20 µL	--	18 mm
	25 µL	--	18 mm
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	05 µL	10 mm	18 mm
	10 µL	--	18 mm
	15 µL	--	18 mm
	20 µL	10 mm	18 mm
	25 µL	13 mm	18 mm

Figure 1. The antibacterial activity of *D. alata* tuber extract was tested against selected bacterial pathogens. Zones of inhibition were observed at different concentrations ranging from 5 to 25 mg/mL.

A. Whole plant of *D. alata* and B. Tuber. C. *Bacillus subtilis*, D. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, E. *Salmonella typhi*.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study show that the tuber extract of *Dioscorea alata* possesses moderate and selective antibacterial activity. The extract demonstrated measurable antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a strain that showed no sensitivity to streptomycin under the present experimental conditions. Although the activity was lower than the standard antibiotic in most cases, the results indicate the presence of bioactive compounds in the tubers and support the need for further detailed phytochemical and minimum inhibitory concentration studies.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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